

Pesticide Exposure and Health Impacts Among Farmers in Karimnagar: A Cross-Sectional Risk Assessment Study

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Abstract:

Background: The World Health Organization estimates nearly 3 million cases of pesticide poisoning annually, resulting in 220,000 deaths, especially in low- and middle-income countries. India, the largest pesticide producer in Asia, presents a significant occupational exposure risk.

Objective: To assess the prevalence of pesticide-related health symptoms among farmers in Karimnagar and evaluate their knowledge and practices regarding pesticide safety.

Methods: A 6-month cross-sectional observational study was conducted among 300 farmers aged 20–75 years using structured questionnaires. Data were analyzed using Chi-square tests.

Results: Of the 300 participants, 93.3% were male. Dermatological symptoms were reported by 55.7% and neurological symptoms by 44.2% of symptomatic individuals. Herbicides showed the highest symptom prevalence (40%), followed by insecticides (22.6%). Only 17.3% of participants adhered to PPE usage. A significant association was found between gender and symptom occurrence ($p = 0.010$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the health hazards of pesticide exposure and the gap between safety awareness and PPE compliance. Regulatory and educational interventions are essential.

Keywords: *Pesticide exposure; Occupational health; Neurological symptoms; Protective equipment; Risk assessment; India; Farmers.*

1. Introduction

The global dependence on **pesticides in agriculture** has escalated rapidly over the past few decades, primarily to meet the food demands of a growing population and to mitigate crop losses from pests, weeds, and fungi [1]. However, this reliance has come at a considerable human cost, particularly for **agricultural workers**, who experience **direct and indirect pesticide exposure** during mixing, spraying, and post-application handling [2,3].

The **World Health Organization (WHO)** estimates that **over 3 million cases of pesticide poisoning** occur worldwide each year, with an estimated **220,000 fatalities**, largely in developing countries where regulatory enforcement and worker training are weak [4,5]. India is a key contributor to this burden, being the **largest producer of pesticides in Asia** and **twelfth globally**, with an annual production exceeding **90,000 metric tons** [6]. This production directly feeds into India's agrarian economy, where **over 56.7% of the population** is engaged in agriculture and therefore at risk of **occupational pesticide exposure** [7].

Pesticides used in farming include **insecticides, herbicides, fungicides, and larvicides**, many of which are categorized as **Class I and II hazardous substances** under WHO and FAO guidelines [8]. Despite this classification, their widespread use continues due to their affordability and effectiveness, often at the expense of **farmer safety**. Acute exposure can cause **neurological, respiratory, gastrointestinal, and dermatological symptoms**, whereas chronic exposure has been linked to **cancer, Parkinson's disease, endocrine disruption, infertility, and birth defects** [9–12].

Mechanistically, many pesticides exert their toxicity via **inhibition of acetylcholinesterase, generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), and mitochondrial dysfunction**, leading to cellular stress and multi-system pathology [13,14]. Additionally, **persistent organic pollutants (POPs)** such as organochlorines are **lipophilic**, bioaccumulate in **adipose tissues**, and have been detected in **maternal blood, breast milk, and placental tissue**, raising long-term public health concerns [15,16].

In India, **unsafe practices** like storing pesticides in food containers, lack of **PPE use**, and **illiteracy** amplify the risk, especially in rural areas with minimal regulatory surveillance [17]. Women and children are often exposed indirectly through contaminated clothing and household dust, placing entire families at risk [18,19].

Given this critical context, the present study was conducted in **Karimnagar district of Telangana**, a major agricultural belt, to evaluate the **extent of pesticide exposure**, assess the **prevalence of self-reported health symptoms**, and examine the **level of awareness and adherence to protective practices** among farmers. The findings aim to inform policy recommendations and contribute to **occupational health risk mitigation** in agricultural settings.

2. Materials and Methods

This prospective, cross-sectional observational study was conducted over a period of six months in the agricultural regions of Karimnagar district, Telangana. The area was selected due to its intensive agricultural activity and the prevalent use of various pesticide formulations in farming practices, particularly for paddy, cotton, and vegetable crops.

A total of 300 participants, comprising farmers and agricultural workers aged between 20 to 75 years, were enrolled through purposive sampling. The study included individuals directly involved in pesticide handling, mixing, and spraying, as well as women indirectly exposed to pesticides through domestic contact or environmental proximity. Individuals below 18 years of age and landowners not engaged in farming operations were excluded from the study.

Data collection was performed using a structured, bilingual questionnaire designed to capture detailed information on sociodemographic characteristics, pesticide usage patterns, frequency and duration of exposure, types of pesticides used, presence of acute health symptoms, and use of personal protective equipment. Participants were interviewed in their local language following informed consent. Ethical clearance for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Vaageswari College of Pharmacy.

The types of pesticides reported by farmers were categorized according to the World Health Organization's (WHO) classification system based on dermal LD₅₀ values. This classification helped stratify the toxicity risk associated with each pesticide type as presented in the table below.

Table 1: WHO Classification of Pesticides by Hazard

WHO Hazard Class	Band Colour	Signal Word	Dermal LD ₅₀ (Solid Formulation)	Dermal LD ₅₀ (Liquid Formulation)
Extremely hazardous (Class Ia)	Red	Very toxic	<10 mg/kg	<40 mg/kg
Highly hazardous (Class Ib)	Red	Toxic	10–100 mg/kg	40–400 mg/kg
Moderately hazardous (Class II)	Yellow	Harmful	100–1000 mg/kg	400–4000 mg/kg

WHO Hazard Class	Band Colour	Signal Word	Dermal LD ₅₀ (Solid Formulation)	Dermal LD ₅₀ (Liquid Formulation)
Slightly hazardous (Class III)	Blue	Caution	>1000 mg/kg	>4000 mg/kg
Unlikely to present acute hazard	Green	Caution	>2000 mg/kg	>4000 mg/kg

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline demographics, pesticide types, and symptom frequencies. Associations between categorical variables, such as type of pesticide, gender, PPE usage, and symptom presence, were tested using Pearson's Chi-square test and Fisher's exact test where appropriate. A p-value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

A total of **300 agricultural workers** were included in the study, with a striking **gender disparity: 280 (93.3%) were males**, while only **20 (6.7%) were females**, reflecting the dominant male participation in pesticide application. The **40–50 years age group** accounted for the largest subset (n=112; 37.3%), followed by those aged **30–40 years (n=98; 32.6%)**, indicating a middle-aged workforce actively engaged in agricultural practices with prolonged exposure history.

Table 1. Age and gender distribution of farmers (N = 300)

Age Group (Years)	Males (n)	Females (n)	Total (n)
20-30	19	7	26
30-40	87	11	98
40-50	110	2	112
50-60	40	0	40
60-70	22	0	22
70-80	2	0	2
Total	280	20	300

Graph.1 A bar graph representation of age and gender distribution

Among the total participants, **70 individuals (23.3%)** reported symptoms attributable to pesticide exposure, whereas **230 (76.6%)** remained asymptomatic. Of those symptomatic, **39 (55.7%)** experienced dermatological issues including erythema, itching, and rashes, while **31 (44.2%)** reported neurological symptoms such as dizziness, headache, and numbness. The majority (28.6%) reported **immediate onset of symptoms** post-exposure; 18.5% had delayed reactions, and 2.8% noted persistent symptoms, indicative of chronic toxicity.

Symptoms were not evenly distributed across all crop types. **Cotton (29%)** and **paddy (22%)** farmers demonstrated the highest symptom burden, reflecting the high-volume, repeated pesticide applications required for these crops. Conversely, those cultivating spinach, mango orchards, or mint reported no symptoms.

Of the 300 farmers, **256 (85.3%)** used insecticides, **22** used fungicides, **20** used herbicides, and only **2** reported larvicide use. Symptom prevalence was highest among **herbicide users (40%)**, followed by insecticide users (**22.6%**), fungicide users (**18.2%**), and none among larvicide users. Despite the apparent trend, statistical analysis showed **no significant association between pesticide type and symptom occurrence (p = 0.698)**, suggesting that exposure pattern, dosage, and application practices may be more critical than chemical class alone.

Table 2. Prevalence of symptoms based on pesticide type used.

Pesticide Type	Users (n)	Symptomatic (n)	Symptom Prevalence (%)
Insecticide	256	58	22.6
Herbicide	20	8	40.0
Fungicide	22	4	18.2
Larvicide	2	0	0.0

Graph.2 A column bar graph representation of symptom prevalence by pesticide type

Although **260 farmers (86.6%)** reported being aware of safety practices, only **52 (17.3%)** actually adhered to the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) such as gloves, masks, and goggles. Among PPE users, only **12 (23%)** experienced symptoms, while **58 symptomatic cases (23.4%)** were from the non-compliant group. This indicates that although PPE use reduced risk, the difference in symptom prevalence between users and non-users was statistically marginal, possibly due to incorrect or inconsistent PPE application.

Table 3. Pesticide safety knowledge and PPE compliance among farmers.

<i>Pesticide safety knowledge and PPE compliance</i>	Yes (n)	No (n)
Knowledge of safety measures	260	40
Practiced PPE usage	52	248
Symptomatic cases (within group)	12	58

Graph.3 A bar graph representation of PPE knowledge and practice

According to WHO dermal LD50-based classification, **114 farmers (38%) used moderately hazardous (Class II) pesticides**, **103 (34.3%) used slightly hazardous (Class III)**, **73 (24.3%) used chemicals considered unlikely to pose acute hazard**, and **10 (3.3%) reported using highly hazardous (Class Ia/Ib) compounds**. Among the symptomatic, **50% were exposed to Class II**, **25.7% to Class III**, and **21.4% to the least hazardous group**. Surprisingly, only 2 of the 10 highly hazardous pesticide users reported symptoms, possibly reflecting underreporting or limited direct handling.

Table 4. Distribution of pesticide usage based on WHO hazard classification.

WHO Classification	Users (n)	Symptomatic (n)	Symptom Rate (%)
Highly Hazardous (Ia/Ib)	10	2	20.0
Moderately Hazardous (Class II)	114	35	30.7
Slightly Hazardous (Class III)	103	18	17.5
Unlikely to Present Acute Hazard	73	15	20.5

Graph.4 A column bar

graph representation of symptoms by WHO Hazard class

Discussion

Pesticide exposure in agricultural settings remains a globally recognized occupational hazard, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where enforcement of safety standards and availability of personal protective equipment (PPE) are often inadequate. The present cross-sectional study conducted in Karimnagar, Telangana, examined 300 farmers and revealed a 23.3% prevalence of pesticide-related symptoms, consistent with prior studies in India and internationally (1,2,3).

The demographic skew toward male participants (93.3%) mirrors patterns observed in other agrarian populations. Middle-aged male farmers were also predominantly exposed in reports from international and Indian sources, reflecting their primary role in manual pesticide application (4,5,6). The cumulative work experience of participants in the 40–50-year age group further implies a chronic exposure profile.

Our clinical findings revealed dermatological (55.7%) and neurological (44.2%) symptoms, consistent with studies describing skin irritation, rashes, dizziness, and headaches as common outcomes of pesticide exposure (7,8,9).

Symptom burden varied significantly by crop, with cotton and paddy farmers most affected, mirroring pesticide-intensive practices observed in these crops elsewhere (12,13). In contrast, negligible symptomatology among spinach and mint cultivators reflects differing pest management requirements and lower pesticide input.

Herbicide users in our study had the highest symptom prevalence (40%), followed by insecticide and fungicide users. Though not statistically significant, this trend supports findings suggesting that herbicides like glyphosate and paraquat have considerable toxicity potential, especially when exposure is frequent and PPE is not consistently used (1,9,14).

Despite high reported awareness of PPE (86.6%), actual usage remained low (17.3%), paralleling trends reported globally (1,13,15). The minimal difference in symptom rates between PPE users and non-users in our study (23% vs. 23.4%) may result from improper use or substandard equipment. Literature has consistently shown that while knowledge may be present, behavioral compliance often lags due to discomfort, affordability issues, or underestimation of risk (13,16,17).

WHO hazard classification revealed most participants used Class II (moderately hazardous) and Class III (slightly hazardous) pesticides. Among symptomatic individuals, 50% had used Class II agents, reinforcing earlier findings that moderately hazardous pesticides, though not as acutely toxic as Class I, are significantly harmful when used without adequate protection (1,8,12).

Interestingly, 21.4% of symptomatic cases in our study involved chemicals classified as unlikely to cause acute toxicity, suggesting potential for chronic, low-dose effects, a phenomenon well described in toxicological literature (12,18,19). Only 2 of 10 users of Class Ia/Ib pesticides reported symptoms, which could be attributed to greater caution during handling or limited usage due to regulatory controls.

In conclusion, our findings affirm that pesticide-related symptoms among Karimnagar farmers are closely linked to exposure patterns, crop type, and PPE adherence, rather than pesticide class alone. These observations call for integrated interventions combining regulatory oversight, farmer training, improved access to PPE, and promotion of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies to reduce health risks.

4. Conclusion

In this study of 300 farmers, **23.3%** reported pesticide-related symptoms—predominantly dermatological (55.7%) and neurological (44.2%). Symptom prevalence was highest among **cotton (29%)** and **paddy (22%)** cultivators. Although **86.6%** were aware of safety measures, only **17.3%** used PPE consistently. Herbicide users exhibited the highest symptom rate (**40%**), and **50%** of symptomatic cases involved moderately hazardous (Class II) pesticides. Notably, **21.4%** of symptoms occurred with low-risk compounds, indicating that exposure dynamics, not just chemical class, drive risk. These findings highlight the urgent need for improved PPE compliance, targeted training, and integrated pest management strategies.

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